

EXPLORING THE DUTY OF CARE OF LEARNERS IN SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the responsibility of care inside educational institutions, specifically schools, and assesses its consequences and issues. It aims to clarify the legal and ethical responsibilities of schools in ensuring student safety and well-being. The study evaluates the extent to which schools meet these responsibilities and identifies possible areas for enhancement. A literature review functions as the study methodology, utilising current studies and academic publications pertinent to the duty of care in education. The study used an interpretive paradigm to analyse how different scholars comprehend the notion and its practical ramifications. This method facilitates an extensive examination of existing practices, legal obligations, and areas in which schools may inadequately protect pupils. This study enhances the discourse on educational policy, emphasising the necessity for sustained attention to student protection and well-being in school settings. The findings highlight the necessity of upholding stringent standards and vigilance about these responsibilities, so ensuring that educational institutions continue to be secure and nurturing environments for students.

Keywords: Duty of care, learner safety, school responsibility, educational law, student well-being.

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper was to examine the duty of care for students in schools. Throughout the article the words “learner” and “student” will be used interchangeably. The principle of duty of care in educational environments is essential for safeguarding the safety and welfare of pupils. The duty of care in educational contexts denotes the legal and ethical responsibility of school administrators to protect the well-being of children [1]. This obligation encompasses taking appropriate measures to avert anticipated harm, including the mitigation of violence and harassment issues. Neglecting this obligation may result in considerable legal liabilities for

educational institutions [2]. Schools serve as fundamental settings for education and growth; hence educators and administrators are legally and ethically required to safeguard students from harm [3]. This responsibility encompasses not just physical safety but also emotional and psychological well-being, underscoring the significance of a supportive and nurturing educational environment [4]. Recent discourse on duty of care has highlighted its ramifications concerning varied student demographics and the obstacles presented by systemic inequities [5]. Comprehending the responsibility of care facilitates adherence to legal norms and promotes a culture of care inside educational institutions, crucial for effective teaching and learning [6]. [7] discovered that numerous schools lack sufficient methods to address sexual abuse, and the impact of hierarchical structures, a culture of silence, and religious authority may obstruct efficient reporting and management of instances within educational institutions. All educational institutions have an obligation to ensure the welfare of their pupils. Nonetheless, the obligation of care is distributed unevenly among schools, with those catering to low-income areas frequently prioritising the material and psychological impacts of poverty. The obligation of care for these schools was highlighted during the Covid-19 school closures, as societal structural inequities became more evident [8].

The purpose of the article is to explore the duty of care in schools. The question which was explored is “How does the duty of care in schools ensure the safety, well-being, and academic development of learners, and what are the legal and ethical responsibilities of educators in fulfilling this duty?”

1.1 GALTUNG'S THEORY OF VIOLENCE

In addressing the duty of care of learners within educational settings, it is imperative to consider Johan Galtung's theory of violence, which distinguishes between direct, structural, and cultural violence. Understanding these dimensions helps educators create safer and more inclusive environments for students.

This article used Galtung's Theory of Violence in exploring the duty of care of learners in schools. [9] posits that violence can be classified into three categories: direct violence, involving physical harm; structural violence, representing systemic inequalities that disadvantage groups; and cultural violence, which legitimises and sustains structural violence through societal norms and values. All manifestations of violence must be handled to build a comprehensive approach for safeguarding students. The duty of care signifies the legal and ethical obligation of educators to provide a safe learning environment. This involves protecting students from physical harm while also addressing structural and cultural factors that may affect their well-being. For instance, if a school fails to recognise and address bullying (a kind of direct violence) or systemic inequalities (structural violence), it undermines its duty of care [10]. Fostering a culture of respect and open dialogue mitigates both direct and cultural violence in educational institutions [11].

In line with Galtung's theory of violence, safety is a global concern that affects learners in schools. In America, Canada, Israel, Kenya and Nigeria learners' safety concerns range from

devastating internal to external school environments, while in South African schools it emanates from natural disasters, bullying, unpleasant infrastructure and gangsterism [12].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

[13] discovered that school administration teams are incapable of properly executing the policies and legislation pertaining to the responsibility of care for learners. This impacts the dynamics within the school community. They advocate for collaboration among administrators, teachers, and School Governing Bodies (SGBs) to foster unity, a culture of respect, human dignity, positive discipline, effective classroom management, and the prevention of any form of abuse against learners.

[14] assert that despite the implementation of national educational policies aimed at addressing safety concerns in schools, the safety of learners remains a significant issue at numerous institutions. An unsafe educational environment adversely impacts learners, resulting in bodily harm, psychological distress, disabilities, and depression. This may also result in a deterioration of learners' performance. Three ways can be employed to meet the duty of care in educational institutions. The authoritarian method encompasses the involvement of law enforcement personnel, implementation of policies, utilisation of security equipment, metal detectors, surveillance cameras, school policing, and zero-tolerance policies. Educational and therapeutic strategies can enhance the school climate by promoting interaction among learners and other stakeholders inside the institution. The educational and therapeutic methods may be employed to fulfil the responsibility of care for learners, encompassing programs such as counselling, conflict resolution training, and peer mediation initiatives.

School managers are responsible for implementing disciplinary policies, including the resolution of complaints related to the anti-bullying policy, to enhance the safety and protection of students within the schools. The successful execution of safety measures may foster a constructive school culture, emphasising discipline, respect, and diversity among all stakeholders in educational institutions [15]. The negligence of school administrators in failing to effectively implement duty of care and discipline policies exposes students to hazardous environments characterised by misconduct, gender-based violence, physical violence, and sexual abuse, potentially resulting in enduring psychological and health issues for the affected individuals. School administrators are tasked with establishing the institutional structure and preventive violence strategies to ensure secure educational environments for students. [16].

Schools can encounter difficulties in fulfilling their duty of care to students due to constitutional rights that provide every citizen the freedom of religion, belief, and opinion. The research conducted by [17]) suggests that schools are encountering difficulties in reconciling the relationship between religion and education due to religious diversity. Addressing disruptive behaviour among students in the classroom is a universal challenge encountered by numerous educators. The demographics of learners are evolving due to detrimental behaviour, which mirrors societal changes and contributes to a rise in misconduct within educational institutions [18]. The situation may be exacerbated by the teachers' deficiency of strategies and competencies

to manage disruptive behaviour. Certain educators may prioritise instructional activities while neglecting the significance of classroom management [18]. Poor classroom management may result in bullying, substance misuse, possession of dangerous weapons, sexual harassment, student altercations, theft, breaches of school behaviour, and disrespect [19].

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child stipulates that children shall be safeguarded from all forms of torture, inhumane or degrading treatment, as well as physical, mental, or sexual abuse, neglect, or maltreatment. Despite policies designed to shield learners from hazardous environments, they persistently endure sexual abuse and various abusive behaviours stemming from cultural practices and corporal punishment at home, intended to intimidate the victim into silence regarding the incidents [20]. One of the professional tasks of teachers is to safeguard human rights and the welfare of learners. They are obligated to fulfil their duty of care by preventing learner sexual abuse, offering support, and informing them about their constitutional rights [21]. Inadequate duty of care in schools also subjects students to sexual abuse activities that they may not completely understand. The victimised students are juveniles and incapable of providing informed permission, lacking the developmental readiness to participate in sexual activity. The sufferers endure emotional and cognitive issues, including diminished attentiveness, reduced self-confidence, and impaired relationships in educational settings [22]. [23] assert that schools are responsible for creating preventative programs that provide students with the essential knowledge and abilities to disclose abuse.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

In this article sources from 1969 to until 2024 were read and analysed.

3.1 Data collection

The major methodology for the study involved a comprehensive literature review for data collection. A literature review is an essential research instrument that entails the analysis and synthesis of current academic studies, reports, and scholarly publications pertinent to a given subject—in this instance, the duty of care in education. The study employed this method to utilise contemporary research and theoretical frameworks from many reliable sources, facilitating an in-depth examination of the topic matter. This compilation comprises peer-reviewed publications, books, and case studies that elucidate the responsibilities and practices associated with the duty of care in educational environments [24]. The literature review facilitated the collection and assessment of existing knowledge regarding the duty of care for learners in educational institutions, offering a comprehensive grasp of how this subject has been treated in various contexts. The data obtained from several scientific investigations enabled the researchers to delineate the existing level of knowledge, pinpointing essential topics, trends, and prevalent practices concerning the protection of pupils. This approach provided a comprehensive overview of the discipline, emphasising both established conclusions and current controversies within the scholarly community.

The gathered data not only summarised and analysed prior research but also played a vital role in pinpointing gaps or areas of inconclusiveness or inconsistency in the research. The review synthesised diverse data, providing a thorough picture of the research landscape regarding duty of care in schools. It offered a more refined comprehension of domains where the existing knowledge is deficient, inconsistent, or requires additional empirical research [25]. This analysis facilitated the identification of prospective research avenues, directing scholars and practitioners to domains necessitating further scrutiny, including the development of legal frameworks, the influence of technology on student welfare monitoring, and the cultural variances in the interpretation and application of duty of care in schools worldwide. Consequently, this literature review methodology not only synthesised existing information regarding the responsibility of care for students in educational institutions but also identified topics warranting further investigation, thereby influencing future academic research and policy discourse.

3.2 Data analysis

The data analysis in this study adhered to the interpretive paradigm, a qualitative methodology that emphasises comprehending the social and contextual realities formed within situations, such as educational settings. The interpretive paradigm posits that reality is socially produced through interactions and shared experiences, with people or groups possessing intricate, subjective interpretations of those events. This framework was especially effective for examining the duty of care in educational institutions, since it seeks to elucidate the intricate and varied perceptions of how diverse stakeholders—such as educators, learners, and administrators—comprehend and experience the notion of duty of care [26]. Interpretivist paradigms aim to elucidate the underlying significance of individuals' behaviours and beliefs, rather than just measuring them. The interpretive approach enabled researchers to examine the diverse and intricate perspectives about the duty of care, transcending superficial observations to investigate its formation by cultural, social, and institutional influences inside the educational setting. This method elucidated the varying conceptions of obligations among stakeholders, the obstacles encountered in executing their duty of care, and how these perceptions may differ based on roles, relationships, and contextual factors.

The utilisation of an interpretive framework in this study was crucial for developing a more profound comprehension of the responsibility of care in educational institutions. It enabled researchers to investigate how educators, personnel, and students engage with the notion in realistic contexts, considering the ethical, emotional, and pragmatic aspects of their obligations. Through the analysis of the lived experiences and interactions of these individuals, the researchers effectively captured the intricacies and nuances of how duty of care is enacted, perceived, and negotiated in everyday school life. This paradigm elucidated the extensive social and institutional factors that influence the obligation of care, including educational policies, legal structures, and cultural norms. It emphasised the intersection of external variables with personal ideas and actions, resulting in a nuanced comprehension of the operationalisation of duty of care within the educational system. The interpretivist approach was essential in elucidating how these

processes alter across many contexts, demonstrating the flexibility and adaptability necessary to address the distinct demands of learners in diverse educational settings.

4. RESULTS

The themes that emerged from the literature review are "Ethics of Care," "Inclusivity in Education," and "Peer Support Systems."

4.1 Ethics of Care

The "ethics of care" notion underscores the moral obligations of educators and leaders to cultivate an atmosphere of empathy and support. This theme examines how educational leaders might establish nurturing communities that emphasise student well-being. In [4] study, the significance of fostering relationships inside educational institutions is emphasised. [4] contends that leadership must be rooted in compassion, which not only increases student participation but also fosters a healthy school environment [4].

4.2 Inclusivity in Education

Inclusivity is essential for educational equity, ensuring that all students, irrespective of their backgrounds or skills, have access to high-quality education. Leaders are crucial in formulating policies and procedures that promote inclusive education. Illustration: A study by [27] demonstrates how educational leaders can adopt inclusive practices through staff training and family engagement to foster supportive learning environments. Their research demonstrates that inclusive leadership is associated with enhanced student results and increased community satisfaction [27].

4.3 Peer Support Systems

Peer support systems in educational institutions, including peer counselling programs, have demonstrated efficacy in tackling problems such as bullying and substance addiction. Educational leaders must enable these systems to empower students. [28] investigated the efficacy of peer counselling at Zimbabwean educational institutions, concluding that these programs markedly diminished occurrences of drug and substance addiction among students. They promote increased participation of all stakeholders in the creation of comprehensive peer support frameworks [28]. By incorporating the ethics of caring, advancing inclusivity, and implementing peer support networks, educational leaders may cultivate environments that boost learning while fostering a feeling of belonging and community.

5. DISCUSSION

Leaders who adopt an ethics of caring framework are inclined to prioritise the welfare of students and staff over strict compliance with policies. During the Covid-19 pandemic, numerous educational leaders encountered the problem of shifting to remote learning. Individuals who addressed this difficulty thoughtfully took into account the varied requirements of their students, including access to technology and mental health resources, rather than just imposing adherence to new laws [29].

[30] asserts that inclusion transcends the mere integration of children with disabilities into regular classes; it necessitates a transformation of educational procedures to address various learning requirements. This transformation necessitates a thorough comprehension of the obstacles to learning and a dedication to eliminating those obstacles via customised teaching methodologies, resources, and support systems [31].

Peer support systems are structured programs in which individuals offer aid and encouragement to each other. These systems are vital in educational settings since they enhance outcomes including academic performance, emotional well-being, and a sense of belonging [32]. Peer counselling programs educate students to offer emotional assistance and direction to their peers. An illustration is the "Peer Support Program" instituted at many high schools; wherein trained students assist their peers in addressing personal difficulties. Research indicates that these interventions diminish occurrences of bullying and enhance overall student satisfaction [33]. Notwithstanding their advantages, peer support systems encounter numerous problems. A major difficulty is the necessity for sufficient training and oversight to guarantee effective assistance. In the absence of adequate coaching, peer supports may experience feelings of being overwhelmed or inadequately prepared to address sensitive matters [34]. Moreover, the dynamics of peer interactions may occasionally result in confrontations or perpetuate undesirable behaviours, especially in adolescent contexts [35]. Peer support networks are essential in educational leadership and management, promoting a culture of collaboration and mutual aid. Although they provide various advantages, meticulous deployment and continuous support are crucial to optimise their efficacy and tackle potential obstacles. The duty of care, grounded in common law, mandates that educators undertake reasonable measures to safeguard children from foreseeable damage [36]. In *Hoffman v. Board of Education* (2004), the court determined that the school neglected its duty of care by inadequately supervising pupils during a physical education session, resulting in an injury. Educators are anticipated to prioritise the welfare of their students, fostering both academic achievement and emotional and social health. [4] asserts that care in education entails cultivating connections that promote trust and reciprocal respect.

Educational institutions must guarantee sufficient oversight during break periods and extracurricular engagements. For instance, if a student sustains an injury during a football game due to insufficient monitoring, the school may be deemed accountable for violating its duty of care [37]. Educators must be sensitive to the emotional and psychological requirements of their students. A teacher observing a notable alteration in a student's behaviour may intervene to address possible bullying or mental health concerns, so fulfilling their ethical obligation of care [38]. The duty of care encompasses the obligation to provide suitable support to all learners,

including individuals with disabilities. The execution of Individualised Education Plans (IEPs) for students with special needs illustrates how educational institutions might meet their duty of care by offering customised learning experiences [39]. Numerous educational institutions encounter financial limitations that hinder their capacity to offer proper support services, leading to inadequate monitoring and care for students (Jones, 2020). Educators frequently lack the training necessary to identify and address children's emotional and psychological needs. Professional development centred on mental health awareness can improve educators' capacity to meet their responsibility of care [40].

Duty of care denotes the legal responsibility of educators to implement reasonable measures to safeguard the safety and well-being of students. This principle is grounded on common law and focusses primarily on harm prevention. Educators must protect kids from physical danger while fostering an environment that promotes their emotional and academic development [41]. If a teacher identifies a possible hazard, such as a broken stair or an incident of bullying, they are obligated to handle these issues swiftly. Neglecting to do so may constitute a violation of their duty of care, making them accountable for any consequent harm [42].

Duty of care denotes the legal responsibility of educators to implement reasonable measures to safeguard the safety and well-being of students. This principle is grounded on common law and focusses primarily on harm prevention. Educators must protect kids from physical danger while fostering an environment that promotes their emotional and academic development [41]. If a teacher recognises a possible threat, such as a broken stair or an incident of bullying, they are obligated to handle these issues without delay. Neglecting to do so may constitute a violation of their duty of care, making them accountable for any ensuing damage [42]. The safety and welfare of students are essential in executing the responsibility of care. Educational institutions must establish rules and practices that safeguard students from physical and psychological harm. This encompasses:

Educational institutions must uphold secure environments, do routine safety drills, and guarantee that personnel are proficient in emergency protocols. Regular fire drills help equip pupils for emergencies and mitigate panic during actual incidents [43]. Educators must identify indicators of emotional distress in pupils and offer suitable assistance or referrals. Initiatives like peer counselling and mental health awareness can greatly enhance a supportive educational atmosphere [28]. Educators must establish inclusive educational settings that address varied learning requirements. This not only satisfies the responsibility of care but also enhances academic achievement. Differentiated instruction and personalised learning plans exemplify tactics that address the academic demands of all learners [44]. Educational institutions are required to ensure a secure learning atmosphere devoid of prejudice and harassment. Noncompliance with these regulatory criteria may result in litigation and substantial financial consequences for educational institutions [45]. Educators are ethically obligated to prioritise the best interests of their students. This encompasses championing their rights and needs, cultivating a culture of respect, and advancing social justice within the educational community. Implementing restorative justice strategies can effectively resolve disagreements among students by fostering healing and understanding instead of punishment [46].

Furthermore, educators ought to participate in continuous professional development to enhance their comprehension and execution of their duty of care. Knowledge of contemporary educational methodologies, legal obligations, and ethical issues is essential for effective teaching and leadership [47].

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the duty of care for learners in educational institutions is an essential obligation that significantly contributes to the safety, welfare, and comprehensive development of pupils. Educational institutions, together with their educators and personnel, are responsible for establishing and sustaining a safe, supportive atmosphere conducive to learning, while protecting students from all forms of harm or injury. This obligation is complex and outside the scope of academic teaching. It includes emotional well-being, promoting positive mental health, ensuring physical safety, and mitigating any hazards that kids may face both on school grounds and during school-related activities such as field excursions, extracurricular programs, and events. Educators and school administrators must be watchful and proactive in recognising potential hazards, including bullying, mental health issues, and physical threats such as dangerous facilities or inappropriate conduct by staff or classmates. By anticipating hazards and implementing requisite protections, they satisfy their legal and ethical duty to act in the best interest of their pupils. This entails the implementation of safety standards, the establishment of explicit behavioural norms, and the provision of emotional assistance to pupils with personal difficulties.

The involvement of the learners is equally significant. Although schools hold the principal responsibility for care, students are anticipated to adhere to established regulations and protocols to safeguard both their own safety and that of their peers. Students enhance the collective safety and well-being of the school community by honouring teachers' authority, collaborating to create a secure learning environment, and being cognisant of their conduct. Furthermore, parents and guardians assume a vital supportive function. By emphasising the significance of compliance with safety measures at home, sustaining transparent communication with the school, and addressing any issues, they facilitate a cohesive link between the school and home environments. The cooperative engagement of educators, staff, students, and parents is vital for effectively executing the responsibility of care. A collective dedication to safety, accountability, and communication underpins a comprehensive educational experience that fosters learners' holistic growth and development. The duty of care at educational institutions is a shared obligation necessitating the active involvement of all stakeholders. When schools diligently fulfil their duty of care, they not only ensure a safe and secure environment but also establish the conditions essential for students to thrive academically, socially, and emotionally, so guaranteeing their future success and well-being.

The criteria used to assess the adequacy of schools' care responsibilities are the following: Schools must implement comprehensive mechanisms to safeguard children from abuse, neglect, bullying, and other hazards. Systematic risk assessments are performed to guarantee the physical and emotional well-being of pupils in the educational setting. Robust processes must be

established for reporting concerns regarding student safety, ensuring clear communication channels for staff, students, and parents. Schools must have a secure and healthful physical environment, encompassing facilities that foster hygiene, availability of potable water, sufficient sustenance, and adequate supervision during physical activity. Appropriate measures must be implemented to ensure students' emotional well-being, encompassing access to counselling services, stress reduction programs, and mental health awareness education. Schools are tasked with overseeing student attendance and resolving truancy concerns. Educational institutions must collaborate with families in instances of chronic absenteeism, helping resolve underlying concerns that may affect attendance. They must evaluate and address the requirements of students with special educational needs, guaranteeing access to tailored support and accommodations. Schools must ensure an environment devoid of discrimination based on race, gender, sexual orientation, or handicap. Policies ought to foster inclusion and uphold respect for diversity. Care responsibilities must encompass the respect for students' cultural, religious, and social backgrounds. They must guarantee that students receive adequate support to achieve their potential via differentiated instruction, remediation for underperforming students, and enrichment programs for those excelling. Proper monitoring is essential, particularly during breaks, sports, and extracurricular activities. The school must be secure, sanitary, and accessible, with amenities including classrooms, restrooms, and outdoor areas in optimal shape. Therefore, schools are required to comply with national and local legislation pertaining to childcare, educational standards, and health and safety.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

A comprehensive school strategy founded on efficient administration, well-defined and dedicated school structures, processes, and resources, together with expertise in understanding and executing school regulations, is advocated to enhance the duty of care for students in educational institutions [48]. Educational institutions must formulate and implement extensive safety protocols encompassing physical security, emotional health, and digital safety. These protocols must be routinely assessed and revised to align with contemporary best practices and new threats. Facilitate Continuous Training for Personnel: Educators, administrators, and school staff must undergo ongoing training in safeguarding, child protection legislation, first aid, mental health awareness, and conflict resolution. This guarantees they are adequately prepared to identify hazards, react to crises, and manage delicate situations. Promote a Supportive Educational Environment: Establishing a good, inclusive, and courteous school culture is crucial for the emotional well-being of students. Educational institutions ought to advocate for anti-bullying initiatives, mental health resources, and peer mentorship programs to foster a sense of belonging among students.

Promote Transparent Communication: Educational institutions ought to create explicit channels of communication among faculty, students, and parents. Promoting learner expression of concerns or reporting of hazardous conditions, alongside providing parents with consistent updates, cultivates trust and teamwork, hence facilitating rapid issue resolution. Establish Comprehensive monitoring Policies: Continuous monitoring must be guaranteed, particularly in

high-risk environments such as playgrounds, sports fields, and during educational excursions. Educational institutions must uphold suitable student-to-staff ratios and guarantee that all professionals comprehend their supervisory duties. Educational institutions can utilise technology, like surveillance systems and electronic attendance records, to oversee school surroundings and improve safety. This facilitates the prompt identification and mitigation of possible dangers while ensuring accountability. Educational institutions ought to establish initiatives that foster emotional resilience and mental well-being, including counselling services, mindfulness practices, and education in emotional intelligence. This guarantees that students receive support in both academic and personal domains. Educational institutions ought to engage parents and the wider community in safety activities. Conducting workshops, supplying resources on safety concerns, and promoting parental involvement in school governance can enhance the collaborative endeavours to safeguard student welfare.

All educational institutions must possess comprehensive emergency preparedness plans, encompassing evacuation procedures, lockdown drills, and methods for addressing crises such as natural disasters or violent acts. These strategies must be implemented consistently to ensure staff and students are acquainted with them. Educational institutions must routinely evaluate the efficacy of their duty of care measures by internal audits, feedback from students and parents, and adherence to regulatory criteria. Ongoing surveillance facilitates prompt modifications and enhancement of safety protocols.

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